

Mathematics - an independent reality or a tool?

A truism - without mathematics there would be no contemporary technological and science-based civilization with all its amenities and gadgets. And it has an almost mesmerising effect on human brain: the beauty of its formal structures, the symmetry, the predictive power...

So, is it the real essence of the Universe, its *spiritus movens*? Plato, the ancient Greek geometry genius thought so when he said: "The knowledge at which geometry aims is the knowledge of the eternal." (*Republic, Book VII*, ~526-527) or "[The Demiurge] began to think of making a moving image of eternity: at the same time as he brought order to the universe, he would make an eternal image, moving according to number, of eternity remaining in unity. This is what we call time." (*Timaeus* 37d). Since then, Plato has become the symbol of what I call 'fetishising' mathematics. It works so well it must be divine; it is the reason, not the result.

Nota bene, even his pupil and opponent, Aristotle, had found it a bit disturbing. He linked the 'idea' to the 'physical world' (*in re*). For him, mathematical structures exist in objects, not beyond them. Take note of this distinction, we will come back to it.

The Platonian view - mathematics first, physical reality second - has persisted over the millennia. Today we still have a sizeable number of respected physicists and philosophers who endorse, to various extents, this line of reasoning. Take Tegmark with his 'Mathematical Universe Hypothesis' (e.g. *Foundations of Physics* 38, 2008, 101–150) or Penrose saying in his "*Road to Reality...*", (2004): "Mathematics is a kind of necessity, virtually conjuring its very self into existence." And let's not forget Wigner's: "The enormous usefulness of mathematics in the natural sciences is something bordering on the mysterious and that there is no rational explanation for it." (*Communications in Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 13, 1960, 1-14). The Neo-Platonists strongly endorse priority of mathematics over the physical world we experience daily. Others, in this vein, wonder why we are capable of understanding the Universe's mechanics at al...

But Aristotle is not alone. Grattan-Guinness, Field, Woit, Frenkel, just to mention a few, disagree with this line of reasoning. For them, the arguments used by the Neo-Platonists smack often of hidden, non-scientific, ontological redundancy and may fail the falsifiability criterion.

Ironically, Wigner himself, in the work mentioned above, says also: "Mathematics is the science of skilful operations with concepts and rules invented just for this purpose." 'Invented'...? Well, either it is the primordial essence of the existence, or it has been invented... Btw., by whom? I'd presume by us...

So, let me share my view of this whole issue - one which some link to 'structural realism'. As we all can see, the world around us shows numerous, non-chaotic, regularities. Why? Because, evidently, the Universe self-regulates itself using 'rules', 'principles', 'physics laws' - whatever we call them. This means that there are regular patterns around. Through observation we have learned to recognise these patterns and code them by creating a language called 'mathematics'.

This is crucial. Mathematics is not the fabric of reality - we have invented the language, not the patterns... It is what happens when an evolved brain compresses the observed patterns into 'laws'.

The lack of complete chaos and the structured complexity of reality also explain the predictive power of this language. The patterns of the observable reality are necessarily hierarchical. One of the reasons might be the spontaneous emergence of complexity - fully within the grasp of the well-understood physics (e.g. see my essay: "*What drives complexity?*", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18659415>). Ergo, it allows us to infer things we have not observed yet, but which are plausible consequences of the already observed and coded patterns. This also explains what Wigner found so mysterious. It is not a miracle, but a structural inevitability. Physics is full of such cases.

Nota bene, most of the invented mathematical structures have not found any practical applications, yet - again, this is a redundancy typical of any natural language... However, the usefulness and... the beauty of it is that someday such applications may be found. This also has happened again and again.

So, Plato and his followers seem to run out of hard, verifiable - and falsifiable - arguments... No deus ex machina or mystical enforcer of the physical reality are needed. Mathematics is a codified outcome of our observations of the objective, repetitive 'laws of physics'... Punto. Ockham is merciless here ...

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